

PSYCHOLOGICAL SCIENCES

MOTIVATION, AUGMENTED REALITY AND ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT IN STUDENTS GROUPS

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ABSTRACT

One of the most common problems we encounter in education and training is lack of motivation. Lack of motivation is an important problem that reduces the success graph of students. This negative picture, which is frequently seen in primary, secondary and university education, is undoubtedly not due to a single cause. Many bio-psycho-social reasons can destroy or weaken motivation. The author searched the main factors that destroy or weaken student's motivation level.

There is a real need for academicians to examine in more detail the factors that cause motivational weakness in university students. This important issue should be addressed not only by scientists but also by the family and social environment at various times and places. Otherwise, if this pessimistic feeling in many students whose motivation is impaired is not treated, it can turn from individual depression into collective and social neurosis. Therefore, all employees related to education and training, whether they are teachers or university academicians, should have a good level of pedagogical formation knowledge. Because it is not enough to just present information to students. At the same time, it is necessary to have a psychosocial and intellectual equipment that can guide them spiritually and morally.

Aim of the study: the main purpose of the research is investigate relation students motivation and achievement, and also the effect of augmented reality factor.

The manuscript has been developed based on literature review material, and according to constructive methodology.

Keywords: Students' personality; motivation; academic achievement, augmented reality.

Literature review:

Academic motivation is defined as a person's desire to achieve success in the field of education (Usher, 2012). The modern approach to the study of academic motivation is also associated with the use of the theory of self-determination by E. Deci and R. Ryan. Supporters of this theory identified three types of motivation: internal (associated with one's own desire), external motivation (associated with the desire of others) and amotivation (lack of desire) (Deci et.al.,2000). Previously, researchers studied the relationship between academic motivation and success in the process of studying at the university (Erten 2014), the possibility of predicting the average grade point in the process of studying using academic motivation (Chetin 2015), considered the problems of the relationship between external and internal motivation (Ayub, 2010), as well as the predominance of external motivation over internal (due to political, economic, social conditions) in students (Triyanto, 2019). Gender characteristics of academic motivation have been studied quite often (Sivirkaya. 2019). In addition, recently researchers have been studying the relationship between the use of modern technologies and academic motivation (Li et al., 2017).

The theory of basic psychological needs arose within the framework of the theory of self-determination by E. Deci and R. Ryan. According to this theory, each person has three basic needs: autonomy, competence and relatedness (Deci et.al., 2001). Satisfaction of basic psychological needs is also of great importance

during the process of studying at university. Thus, students whose basic psychological needs were satisfied were more likely to want to participate in various projects during their studies, and demonstrated an interest in studying more complex and advanced courses (Trenshaw, 2016). At the same time, unsatisfied basic psychological needs are associated with the fact that students more often experience stress (for example, during exams), and anxiety during high school (Corderio, 2016).

The relationship between basic psychological needs, academic motivation and alienation from learning - Previous studies have established a relationship between alienation and academic motivation in the process of learning at school (Harsher, 2018). Researchers also found a significant negative effect in the absence of satisfaction of basic psychological needs and alienation from learning (Mahmaoudi, 2015).

Thus, it was demonstrated that basic psychological needs are predictors in relation to academic motivation (Harsher, 2018).

Some points that should not be overlooked in motivation analyses are as follows. Success in any job is to achieve what is desired. Happiness, on the other hand, is to love what is achieved. Therefore, the ideal motivation approach should not only be success.

It is also extremely important that the things achieved are loved by the relevant people. Although it is seen in every walk of life, sometimes quite opposite behaviors are seen in university students in particular. For example, a person who finishes a bachelor's degree that he does not like cannot be productive in this field.

However, if he likes it, he will be more dynamic. And in order to be both successful and happy, it is necessary to determine the motivation dynamics very well. Being eager for the ideal job, profession or school, designing distant and near goals by consulting, starting work, not leaving room for boredom, being able to say yes to what you want and no to what you do not want, are the main dynamics for motivation ability.

When a general evaluation is made from a psychoanalytic perspective, there are generally two reasons for the lack of motivation in students. Preparatory and stimulating reasons. While age, gender, genetic factors and family structure play an important role in the predisposing factors, the negative aspects related to the person's lifestyle, economic indicators and nutritional habits are more prominent in the stimulating factors. If a person living in a moderate family environment does not have any pathological problems, it is expected that their motivational ability is normal. However, biosychosocial life differences affect motivational ability positively or negatively. Maslow's hierarchical definition of drives and motives is generally proportional to needs (Maslow, 2001). These needs can be physiological as well as psychological in origin and can be related to emotions and passions. However, although motives are related to all the needs of people and are almost the same in every person, the negative elements that cause motivational weakness may differ from person to person. For example, although economic inadequacy and poverty affect some students very negatively, they do not affect others at all, but family conflicts affect many students very much.

Today, with the changing and developing technology, different concepts have started to take their place in the literature. One of the most popular of these concepts is the concept of "augmented reality". Augmented reality is now encountered in almost every field, and one of the areas where it is used is education. With the widespread use of mobile devices, applications used in the field of education are updated and show a rapid increase. With the use of augmented reality applications in education, useful content is made fun and interesting and presented to students (Ersoy 2016).

According to Azuma (1997), augmented reality is a type of virtual environment or a more intensively used form of virtual reality. According to Özarıslan (2011), it is an environment where the real world and the virtual world come together in real time and reach the user in the same sensory area. In other words, augmented reality is an environment consisting of the whole of real and virtual objects, created with virtual objects placed on the real world environment in order to enhance the experience (Erbař & Demirer, 2014). Thanks to augmented reality, a rich virtual environment can be created by combining data such as media and GPS location information obtained from reality and information tools (Zachary, Ryder, Hicinbotham, & Bracken, 1997). This technology can also be used on different platforms such as desktop and laptop computers, portable devices and smartphones (Kirner, Reis, & Kirner, 2012). Thus, users can communicate with objects using different technological devices. Based on these definitions in the literature, it is possible to briefly define augmented reality

as interactive environments that emerge by adding the functionality of the virtual world to the real world.

Augmented reality is an alternative computer-aided education/training activity. Although computer-aided education and training activities have been used for a relatively long time, augmented reality promises more capabilities with similar technology. On the other hand, when the literature is examined, there are no studies comparing augmented reality applications that offer alternative capabilities with traditional computer-aided education applications.

The results show that instructional activities carried out with the help of augmented reality have quite positive effects on students compared to other computer-aided instructional applications. There are obvious differences in student achievement and certain types of motivation. This gives the impression that integrating augmented reality activities into instructional applications will yield positive results. The fact that the results do not show significant differences in terms of classes as well as boys and girls gives confidence in terms of adaptation to the classroom environment.

The level of external motivation of undergraduate students is higher than that of master's students. Often, admission to university becomes mandatory for young people. They cannot understand what exactly they want to do, often make mistakes in choosing a specialty, but still continue their studies. This is due, among other things, to the difficulties of transferring within one university, to another university, etc. This result confirms the previously obtained findings, which also noted a high level of external motivation of undergraduate students.

Master's students have lower rates of self-development and self-esteem. This result may be due to the fact that they evaluate courses and their own achievements in them differently than undergraduate students do. For them, more important are not grades and knowledge, but experience and competencies that they can develop during their studies. Previous studies demonstrate that students during their studies in a master's program begin to evaluate subjects in accordance with the extent to which knowledge and skills are relevant to their work experience. Also, students in the master's program feel more able to influence their studies and have strong beliefs about their necessity. The efforts made during the master's program are purposeful: students themselves can choose courses related to their professional interests. In contrast, undergraduate students do not always know their professional specialization. In general, the obtained results were confirmed in other studies, which demonstrated that students in the master's program show greater interest and understanding of the necessity and purpose of their studies.

The authors found that students who feel a high level of satisfaction of basic needs, a high level of academic motivation and a low level of alienation from learning are most often first-year full-time students. Such results may be associated with the process of entering the university and the process of adaptation to new educational conditions. That is, these students are more motivated to study and expect support and understanding from teachers. This is due to their expectations

of the educational process as interesting, easy and related to the future profession that they like. The results obtained by the authors are consistent with the results of an earlier study, which found that first-year students have a high level of motivation. However, the cited studies also found that, as a rule, a high level of motivation is associated with continuous “college-university” learning and self-confidence in students. That is, students who studied after college had higher academic performance scores in disciplines than those students who entered after school.

Conclusion: Based on the literature review, three groups of students studying at the university were identified and differed in the psychological characteristics studied. The first group is characterized by a high level of need to satisfy basic needs, “positively directed” academic motives (cognitive, achievements, self-development), etc., a low level of alienation from learning.

For the second group, basic needs are expressed to a lesser extent, academic motives are associated with external factors, the level of alienation also increases. The third group is characterized by a minimal level of expression of basic needs, academic motives are also at low values, and amotivation is the most expressed, but, unlike the previous groups, students from this group demonstrate the highest values for alienation from learning.

The study, the results of which are presented in the article, is of a “cross-sectional” nature. In the future, in addition to increasing the number of subjects participating in the survey, it is recommended to use other methods of psychological diagnostics: semi-structured interviews, focus groups, etc. In addition, it is advisable to conduct a similar study in other universities (in different cities) and compare the results obtained with each other.

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